

Social Media Adoption for Customer Relations and Organizational Effectiveness of Deposit Money Banks in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness of deposit money banks in Bayelsa State. The objectives of this study was to examine the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and the measures of organizational effectiveness (goal attainment and competitiveness), these guided the formulation of the research hypotheses as well as the development of the research questionnaire. One hundred and thirty six copies of the research questionnaire were distributed to respondents who are bank management cadre employees cutting across the five deposit money banks constitute the sample size for this study which were determined using the Taro Yamane's sample size determination formula. However, only one hundred and ten (110) copies of the questionnaire were valid for the analysis, these valid questionnaire were analyzed using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient and the summary of our results revealed that strong positive relationship exist between social media adoption for customer relations and the measures of organizational effectiveness. The study thus concluded that social media communication ensures a better performance for the deposit money banks in Bayelsa State and consequently, organizational effectiveness. Based on the findings the following recommendations were proffered: Management of the deposit money banks in Bayelsa State and indeed other States should build a strong media space that will create an opportunity for the banks to reach out to their various customers in an effective interrelations that will allow the banks identify and define the challenges of customers and work fast to resolve such challenges; deposit money banks should create an active social media platform the will allow a two way flow of information between the banks and their customer to enable entertain customers complains and make quick and swift response to attend to the general needs of their customers.

KEYWORDS: Social Media Adoption; Customer Relations, Organizational Effectiveness; Goal Attainment; Competitiveness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Banks are deliberately formed to achieve certain goals. Organizations construct strategies for the achievement of set goals that develop organizational structures and set goals. This allows companies to perform regular assessments to determine the level of goals achieved. Organizational effectiveness is called the process of determining the level of performance (Kimani, 2015). An organizational success or organizational value, which is associated to the fulfillment of the objective, is the idea of organizational efficiency. The efficiency of the organization as such describes how well it meets its desired aims and goals.

According to Onwuchekwa (1999), an efficiency assessment examines an organization's performance with respect to certain specific requirements. Tsitsi, Contogiannis and Jembere (2013) argue that organizational effectiveness is to the extent that an organization, as a social system with the available resources and resources, meets its objectives without impairing its means and resources and without putting its members under excessive pressure.

Study by Vinitwatanakhun (2008) showed that organizational efficiencies should focus on personnel and organizations and enable people obtain skills and self-esteem to regulate and find security and support for the changing environment. The most affected by scientific research, as Baker and Branch (2002) pointed out, are the organizations, laboratories and institutions that need effective management, increased accountability and work with limited resources to enhance their efficacy. Although the managers in these businesses are keen to increase their effectiveness, they perceive themselves first as scientists and later as

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managers. However, they must address the challenges of organization and the efficiency of the system. In their research, conduct, sponsorship and design and management, they are obligated to be inventive.

The way companies connect with existing and expected clients is significantly modified by technological improvements, more market competitors, mundialisation, economic developments, dynamic buying patterns and changing environment (Njeri, 2014; Siamagka et al., 2015). Compelling firms adapt quickly and skillfully to achieve a competitive edge compared to other competitors in order to improve their business performance (Dodokh, 2017). Organizations are therefore required to build livelihoods and advances methods (Franco et al., 2016). The participation of organizations in social media use is one of these techniques (Akmese et al., 2016). The adoption and use of the social media has lately earned prominent attention among enterprises, such as in several different sectors (Icha and Agwu, 2016). (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) highlighted that "the web based apps that build on web 2.0's ideological and technological basis and enable user-generated content to be created and exchanged."

The use of social media was therefore considered helpful to help improve the consumer base (Bhanot, 2009). It increases efficiency and efficiency (Constantine, 2013). It lowers costs (Harris & Rea, 2009). It helps companies to partner with other companies (Braskov, 2011). It helps companies understand the wants of customers (Parveen et al., 2016). It enhances employee communication and cooperation (Meske & Stieglitz, 2013). It encourages companies to meet client requirements (Parveen et al., 2016). It promotes traffic and exposure (Stelzner, 2014). It creates links between businesses and consumers (Icha & Agwu, 2016). It enhances the linkage (Cachia, 2008). And it's a great instrument to mobilize companies to take chances, invest in new goods to customer satisfaction, improve feedback and improve the brand image (ElTantawy & Wiest, 2011; Parveen et al., 2016).

On the relationships between social media adoption and organizational efficiency in deposit-money institutions, nothing has been done. Therefore, this study assesses the empirical relation between social media acceptance for customer relations and the organization's efficiency.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Social media networking at the workplace has been touted as the most significant business developments of the 21st century since it has added another dimension to the way people communicate (Ray, 2008) and organizations are increasingly adopting social media usage for consumer relations and outreach; employee participation and connection with other organizations (Munene & Nyaribo, 2013). Studies show that companies across the globe have adopted social networking strategies with the aim of improving productivity (Turban, Bolloju & Liang, 2011). Likewise, social media has also been used as a tool of promoting entrepreneurial growth (Jagongo & Kinyua, 2013).

It is thus significant for companies to clearly distinguish the benefits and drawbacks of social media networks on employee productivity. It is vital to develop a critical mass of empirical evidence to show the pros and cons of social media to the employee and organizational productivity. So far, the majority of the studies carried out on the impacts of social media networks have been in the developed countries with little emphasis on the manufacturing sector in the developing world. A study by Ferreira and Du Plessis (2009) focused only on the university faculties in South Africa while examining effects of social networking on employee productivity. Similar study by Nah and Saxton (2013) only looked at the usage of social media in non-profit organizations.

Further, majority of the studies that argue that using social networking sites reduces productivity in the workplace focus primary only on the time wasted because of social networking at the work place (Account emps, 2010; Nucleus, 2009; Rooksby, et al., 2009). These studies have little or no emphasis on the intrinsic impacts e.g. on motivation; creativity; job satisfaction of social media on employee productivity. Furthermore, these studies have been carried out in the USA where the prevailing conditions may not reflect the Nigerian situation. Munene and Nyaribo (2013) examined the effects of social media participation in the workplace on employee productivity with a limited focus on the amount of time spent by employees on the social media sites.

The major problem of this study is that extant literature in the area of social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness is relatively lacking in extant literature, in the banking sector particularly in Bayelsa State, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, there is no empirical study on social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness as it relates to deposit money banks. In other words, little has been done with regards to examining the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness in Bayelsa State. This study therefore shall investigate the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness of deposit money banks in Bayelsa State.

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1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to determine the extent of relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness of deposit money banks in Bayelsa State. The specifically objectives include:

1. To ascertain the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and goal-attainment of deposit money banks in Bayelsa State
2. To evaluate the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and competitiveness of deposit money banks in Bayelsa State

2.0 SYNOPSIS OF LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Social Media Adoption for Customer Relations

Social media has drastically altered customer-organization connections by facilitating two-way contact (Hoyer & MacInnis, 2010). Furthermore, social media websites give enterprises with the opportunity to interact with prospective and current customers in order to increase the sense of intimacy in the customer connection (Mersey et al., 2010). As a result, social media has not only changed the way organizations and their brands connect with customers, but it has also revolutionized the way business is conducted in a variety of ways (Leeflang et al., 2014; Patino et al., 2012; Schulz & Peltier, 2013).

For example, actively advertising the organization through trending methods; i.e. like using hashtags on Facebook and Twitter helps to boost brand awareness and reliability (Caruso, 2016). "The Internet's power makes it simpler for people to fall in love with you faster. However, be aware that it also makes it simpler for them to fall out of love with you faster; it is a double-edged sword" (Scott, 2009, p.11). As a result, customers think that social media sites are a service channel via which they can interact with businesses in real time, where customers frequently attempt to stay up with a brand's products and promotional activities by monitoring these sites (Mangold & Foulds, 2009).

Consequently, today's consumers are extra inelegant, knowledgeable, and tough; as a result, companies must be approachable and available at all times in each social media communication channel, such as Facebook, Twitter, and Blogs (Gordhamer, 2009). Some firms proved that by responding fast to clients, there by readily reversing unfavorable feelings of customers (Bughin, 2015). Accordingly, giving rich information and improved customer service as soon as possible helps to enhance annual sales and financial gain, connects businesses to customers, builds relationships, and cultivates those ties (Coen, 2016; Copp, 2016; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

2.2 Organizational Effectiveness and its Measures

An organization is a planned social unit that is purposefully formed to achieve specified aims (Malik et al., 2011). Formal social groups of people have been built and reconstructed for specific reasons since the days of Pharaohs erecting pyramids and Chinese emperors creating irrigation systems. Etzioni (cited in Malik et al., 2011) noted three specific attributes of organizations: (1) non-random and planned divisions of labor, power, and communication responsibilities to support the achievement of specific goals; (2) the presence of one or more power centres (i.e., dominant coalitions) that pushes the organization's concentrated efforts toward its goals; and (3) the presence of one or more power centers (i.e., dominating coalitions) that drive the organization's intense efforts toward its goals; and (3) personnel replacement, in which undesirable members can be dismissed and others allocated their duties. These qualities expand on Parsons' (quoted in Malik et al., 2011) definition of an organization and incorporate the notions of power, politics, and organizational member substitutability.

The concept of organizational effectiveness, in principle, is at the foundation of all organizational models. In organizational research, it is essentially the ultimate dependent variable. Given the abundance of writing and study on organizational success, there is no agreement on how to define, measure, and explain the idea. As a result, determining the most relevant lines for distinguishing between effective and ineffective companies is a key issue for organizational evaluation (Zheng, Yang & McLean, 2010).

Organizational effectiveness is described as the extent to be achieved by an organization (the topic of organizational efficiency stressed process control, management of information and the foals setting) (Denison, Haaland & Goelzer, 2004). For the analysis of organizational features, Muthiah and Huang (2016) identified fourteen organizational efficiency variables in the four general categories. In addition to the roles of leaders, management leadership skills in the process of culture transformation are also vital to the effectiveness of individuals and organizations. Efficiency, punctuality, smooth operation and predictability are the most important factors for efficiency in a hierarchy culture.

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The effective organizational function and productivity of the employees inside the performing organization are the interrelated and synchronized factors. This indicates that, if one is maintained, the other has a beneficial consequence or a positive impact on the other (OE or employee productivity). The other has the same effect. For example, if an employee has the information, abilities and attitudes necessary for his immediate position under challenge & practice of HR functions, it implies that he/she adds a good contribution to his/her team, section, department and department as well as to the company.

Organizational effectiveness can therefore be accomplished based on the culture, business environment, structure, processes, systems, and technology levels and staff productivity of the organization. In turn, employees' productivity depends on the HR system. In order for firms to achieve better organizational performance, their talents and their business strategy might be a lasting competitive advantage. Fusion or acquisition, restructuring or business strategy adjustments are examples of fundamental changes in the organizations, which create a strong requirement for procedures and systems to focus and restore the organization's ability to function.

In terms of organizational success, the main operating theory is that control encourages efficiency (waste removal and redundancy) and hence efficiency. Hierarchical organizations, such as the Rivers State Internal Revenue Service, are considered only effective where these major features are achieved. The most valued criteria for effectiveness in a market culture are the achievement of goals, the surpassing of competition, increased market share and the acquisition of significant financial returns. The prevalent operational hypothesis that drives corporate performance is that competition gives encouragement to increased productivity and thus to higher efficiency levels.

In organizations it is difficult to assess effectiveness as a notion in organisation (Daft, 2018; Moon-Gi, 2014; Malik et al., 2011). A range of variables at the organizational and departmental level is taken into account. It assesses how far the organization's varied objectives are met. Organization diversified and fragmented carry out a variety of tasks with different outcomes at the same time (Weick & Daft, 2012). Managers have difficulty assessing performance for purposes not accurate or quantitative (Blenkhorn & Gaber, 2015). Nonetheless, strategically tied performance measurement can help firms achieve their aims (Rose, 2011).

2.2.1 Goal Attainment: The aim of Christensen, Lægreid, Ronnes and Rovik (2007) was to describe the broad principles for action as a collection of ideas. These objectives provide a foundation for public management actions. The objective of an organization is to achieve a desired state of affairs. Its purpose is the consequence of the efforts of the organization. Objectives shape the management of companies as much as the organizations shape its objectives. The efficacy of every organization is assessed on the basis of its objectives (Daft, 2010).

Management gives employees a sense of direction and the activities of employees aim towards updating the objectives of the company (Cummings & Worley, 2015). Objectives contribute to motivate staff to specified objectives. Specific high objectives can also considerably improve employee performance as people want to focus on their actions and efforts. Suitable objectives are a set of limits on employee conduct, activities and decision-making, which enables employees to operate within organizationally acceptable boundaries. Goals assist establish acceptable organizational structure decisions, innovation, the welfare of employees, etc. They also offer standards for evaluation performance, be it in terms of profitability, the units produced, the contentment of the employees, the level of innovation and customer complaints (Daft, 2010).

The objectives of public institutions are occasionally political, for they are mainly led by politicians (Halachmi & Gianakis, 2002). Slack and Parent (2006:38, 41) states that goals give management and other staff with guidance on decision-making, performance assessment, elimination of uncertainties, direction and motivation, as well as corporate legitimacy. They are tools used to translate the overall declaration of purpose, goals and strategy into meaningful instructions for organization. Good relationships between companies and employees are achieved if alignment of objectives is reached. When there is congruence of goals, employees are well motivated and happy.

2.2.2 Competitiveness: Competitiveness means if it is linked to a feature that is appreciated on the market or by the organization's customers. The customers want to comprehend the distinction between the services or goods of the company and its competitive characteristics. These changes pertain to certain product or system qualities that are essential for customers to buy services or products. The qualities or features of services and their distribution methods are the variables which affect the perceptions, usability and availability of customers' services or products. Some examples are the happiness with the service, the

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pricing and the diversity of such features. The key procurement criteria are the factors and criteria that customers utilize for their evaluation and decision making. They may differ for different businesses and segments of the particular market (Javidan, 2018). Resources and organisation's assets alone in generating competitiveness in diverse firms are now no longer enough, according to Gupta et al. (2009) To upgrade competitiveness, a business must be able to use and exploit its assets accurately. It may be characterized as an ability to handle and cope with a particular set of assets facing competition and to utilize accessible sources, which include ability and new gates to enhance new types of services, as the potential grows over years. An organization has an extremely important advantage while applying a cost management method while at the same time concentrating on the actions of other associated competitors (Clulow et al., 2003). It is essential that the company integrates several strategic approaches, over which it has considerable strength and the assets it can develop and deliver significant benefits, in order that the benefits of existing resources can be efficient (Clulow et al., 2003).

2.3 Social Media Adoption for Customer Relations and Organizational Effectiveness

In competitive businesses where technological expertise is critical to exploring technologies, core technology and autonomous R&D choices, including the freedom to explore the potential of innovation, are extremely significant (Huang, 2011). Using social media like technologies allows companies to communicate openly with customers that might affect the image or brand of the businesses and their innovative image as market leaders (Zyl, 2009).

One of the important uses of social media is that client communications, feedback and opinions can stimulate innovation (Matuszak, 2007; Tapscott & Williams, 2006). Small industries therefore need to understand how their brands and services can be influenced by electronic word-of-mouth communication in social media, and features such as participation, social connections, innovation and experience are the main elements that contribute to spreading electronic word-of-mouth on social network (Leung & Baloglu, 2015).

Social media can perform a key part in the future of marketing; it can replace customer distress with commitment outside, and can help shift the conventional control focus internally with an open and cooperative strategy that promotes business success in a more modern context (Harris & Rae, 2009). Social media companies are keen to take risks, invest in new products and services to satisfy their clients and to receive better feedback. Social media also boost digital marketing and promotion, customer service issues management, new ideas development and customer relationships (Solis, 2010). Similarly social media organizations are likely to transform in a more modern and inventive way from the conventional way of doing company (Parveen et al., 2016). Therefore, we hypothesize:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and goal-attainment of deposit money banks in Bayelsa State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and competitiveness of deposit money banks in Bayelsa State.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

2.4.1 Social exchange theory

The theory of social exchange is a broad conceptual paradigm covering a variety of fields of social science, such as administration and social psychology. It is not a single theory but, despite its name, is better understood as a collection of concepts (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). There are a number of common aspects in all theories of the social trade. All theories of social trade treat social activity as a sequence of sequential transactions between two or more parties (Mitchell, Cropanzano & Quisenberry, 2012). Resources are traded in a reciprocal way in which one party tends to pay back another party's good (or occasionally poor) actions (Gergen, 1969; Gouldner, 1960).

The quality of these discussions is occasionally determined by the actor-target connection (Blau, 1964). Economic contacts often include less trust and more active supervision, while social exchanges are usually open, involving greater confidence and freedom (Organ, 1988, 1990). Based on these clear notions, the theory of social exchange is one of the conceptual framework most durable and frequently employed (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Many of the main themes in organizational behavior have at one time been analyzed by use of the theory of social exchange. This conceptual approach has been used to analyze the conduct of an organizational citizen (Organ, 1988, 1990); commitment (Bishop, Scott & Burroughs, 2000), fairness (Tepper and Taylor, 2003) and supervisory and organizational assistance (Ladd & Henry, 2000).

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The ideas of this theory indicate that each encounter involves the trade of commodities and services and that people aim to get as much from others as they have. The theory explains how we feel about a relationship to someone else, according to the perspective we give: how we balance our relationship with what we receive out of it, what sort of connection we deserve, and how we have a better connection with someone else (Rashad, 2013). The theory is built on an interchange of awards and costs to characterize the results values for individuals from various scenarios.

There are two assumptions in the theory of social exchange. Firstly, the character of man and secondly, the quality of connections. Assuming the nature of human conduct, people want pay and prizes and at the same time try to avoid sanctions (West & Turner, 2007). The underlying hypothesis is that people seek the positive result in consideration of the advantages and costs of relationships, Helm, Rolfes and Günter (2006). In result, the level of achievement would be maximized (Helm, Rolfes & Günter, 2006). In addition, people are sensible beings. "Rational entities who try to influence their circumstances so as to achieve specified goals" in order to optimize their own benefits (Gardner, Paul & Patel, 1995).

2.5 Empirical Review

Nyambu (2013) aimed to establish the effect of SM marketing on performance of telecommunication organization in Kenya; the Safaricom Ltd's cases are based on a 2013 customer relations and logistics department survey aimed at 48 employees at Safaricom Ltd headquarters in the West Countries. The regression study revealed that SM increased the company's performance by offering a low-cost marketing platform compared to other existing types of marketing.

Tajudeen (2014) investigated "the factors that influence the social media usage, the various purposes of using social media, and its subsequent impact on organizational performances among Malaysian firms for year 2012 based on a mixed method approach". This consists of an analysis of the online content of the Facebook pages for 567 companies. Profound interviews with six firms listed in the Kuala Lumpur Börse's principal board, who were efficiently employing social media from five different industries. In addition, surveying methods were applied to key informants such as the senior managers from the communications department or marketing departments or the head of the six hundred and sixty-four organizations' social media team. Analyses reveal that SM uses have a stronger and favorable impact on customer service, accessibility, marketing cost reduction and customer service activities in terms of organizational performance.

Karjaluoort *et al.* (2015) tried to examine the relationship between social media activities in an organization and two outcomes, namely, business reputation and financial success in a survey conducted by 9,802 respondents of varied ages, gender and regional groupings from 59 firms operating in Finland in 2013. The results of the two-tails correlation of Pearson show that the social media activities of a business are only partly linked to financial performance and not tied to the reputation of a company.

Akmese *et al.* (2016) is about the association between financial performances of eleven tourism enterprises trading on BIST for 2014 analysis and evaluation on the basis of information gained from the public disclosure platform and BIST's official Web site based on the link between net sales, price/earnings ratios, etc.) and efficient social media usage. The findings of the Mann-Whitney U test show that the usage of social media in BIST-traded firms has a favorable effect on the net profit, value of the market, net sales value and a company's price-to-earnings ratio.

Dodokh (2017) aimed to investigate the impact of social media usage in Dead Sea products firms in Jordan on organizational performance based on a survey that was administered to one hundred and sixty-nine managers and supervisors working at twenty Dead Sea products firms. The results have demonstrated that the use of the social media is favorable in terms of quick adjustment, market time, cost reductions, satisfaction and innovation for the organizational performance in Dead Sea products companies in Jordan.

Ahmad *et al.* (2018) presented a quantitative survey to explore factors that influenced social media adoption by SMEs in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), and its impact on performance. Questionnaires were utilized to obtain data on a random sample of SMEs operating in the UAE from targeted owner-managers or CEOs. One hundred and forty-four reactions were analyzed using partial least squares and SEM methods. The results reveal that use of social media has little impact on the performance of SMEs.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The survey design was the favorite research design for this investigation. The choice of this survey design by researchers is based on their relative advantages with other research designs, in relation to the nature of the subject (human being) being studied.

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Baridam (1990) distinguished between experimental and quasi-experimental designs to illustrate his opposition to experimental design. The almost experimental design is sometimes dubbed "survey," which is based on that in order to control or modify the subject variables for the aim of primary data generation. The study is experimental where adjustment of the variables is feasible. When it is not possible to manipulate the variables, the study becomes a "survey" .Since we have already seen or are seeing our topic matter and variables; the survey design was regarded appropriate. The work of Zeb-Obipi (2007) Cooper & Schindler is supporting this position (2001).

3.2 Population for the Study

Population is a census of all objects or subjects with features or knowledge of the phenomenon examined (Barney, 2000). In general, a research public is a big collection of people, organizations or things, the main subject of a scientific inquiry. Research is carried out for the benefit of the population (Hully et al., 1998).A researcher is a whole series of subjects that are in a researcher's attention (Okeafor, 2002). The target population of this study therefore comprised of the management level employees of five major deposit money banks with international business authorization operating in Bayelsa State, the choice of only five deposit money banks was premised on the convenience of the researcher, therefore, the personal judgement of the researcher informed the selection of only five banks, however the simple random technique of sample selection was adopted to determine the actual deposit money banks that will constitute elements of the sample frame.

3.3 Sample Size Determination

The researchers have decided on the Taro Yamane's sample size determination form in order to determine the sample size of this investigation. The essence of the findings a sample size corresponds to the generalization of the study results by the researcher to the relevant population (Haslam&McGarthy, 1998). Anyanwu (2005) expressed the view that a researcher uses probability sampling to draw an example from the population form, which provides extensive information to ensure that the results are authentically generalized. Thus the Taro Yamane's formula guided the researcher in arriving at the sample size for this study which served as the basis upon which the researchers generalized on the entire population of the study. The Taro Yamane's formulae were used with a 95 percent confidence interval (i.e. 0.05 chances that the sample is distributed in the same way as the population). Thus, the level of significance (e) is 0.05.

The Taro Yamane's formula is

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = Sample Size Sought

e = Level of Significance

N = Population Size

Therefore,

$$n = \frac{206}{1+206(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1+170(0.0025)}{206}$$

$$n = \frac{1+0.515}{206}$$

$$n = 1.515$$

$$n = 136$$

Therefore, the sample size for this study consisted of one hundred and thirty-six (136) respondents cutting across the five deposit money banks in Bayelsa State selected for this study.

Again this sample size of one hundred and thirty six (136) respondents were proportionally distributed among the five (5) regional offices of the deposit money banks selected for this study, using Bowley's (1964) proportional allocation formula,

$$\text{given as; } nh = \frac{nNh}{N}$$

Where nh	=	Number of units allocated to each organization
n	=	Sample size
Nh	=	Number of employees in each organization
N	=	Population size

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Substituting the formula above accordingly, the sample size distribution among the five deposit money banks are given below:

Table 3.1: Bowley's Optimum Size Distribution

S/N	GSM Firms	Accessible Population	Sample Size
	First Bank	49	$\frac{136 \times 49}{206} = 32$
	Guarantee Trust Bank	38	$\frac{136 \times 38}{206} = 26$
	Union Bank	46	$\frac{136 \times 46}{206} = 30$
	Fidelity Bank	37	$\frac{136 \times 37}{206} = 24$
	Zenith Bank	36	$\frac{136 \times 36}{206} = 24$
	Total	206	136

Source: Research survey, 2021.

Having used the Bowley's optimum size distribution, the random sampling technique was used to select the sample elements in each stratum to obtain the applicable sample size for that stratum. Each population element was assigned a number varying from one (1) to 49, 38, 46, 37 and 36 for the strata respectively. The selection process continued in each stratum until the sample size of each (32, 26, 30, 24 & 24) was obtained. The sample size therefore, represents 66% of the total accessible population.

3.4 Reliability of Instrument

The consistency or accuracy of a measurement is considered as reliability. Therefore, if consistent a measurement is said to be trustworthy (Baridan, 2005). The reason for the reliability test is to assess whether the instrument will generate the same results numerous times when administered or the level of consistency in response to a specific sample when intra-rater is used. Furlong, Lovelace and Lovelace (2000) observed that the alpha test coefficient of Cronbach is a measurement measuring scale for the dependability intraterrestrials of a device. Nunally (1978) and Ahiauzu (2006) said that recently, a coefficient of 0.70 and higher was accepted by researchers. In this study, Cronbach was utilized with the help of the SPSS software program in testing for dependability.

3.5 Methods of Data Analysis

Zeb-Obipi (2007) explains that the technique of data analysis includes establishing data preparation and presentation plans (elementary analyzes), testing hypothesis (statistical analysis) and interpretation of outcomes based on data produced and tested accordingly. This leads to three fundamental processes being recognized (primary analysis, secondary analysis and tertiary analysis).

The primary analysis consequently entailed the preparation of data, including the editing, coding and scoring of the acquired information for the objectives of this study. In particular, data tabulation, including statistical tables, frequency distribution and graphical display, were also included in the main analysis.

Due to the employment of three procedures, which included a statistical test (proving relations and differences), secondary analysis, could also be used, meaning testing (significance of differences and associations) and decision testing (acceptance and rejection of hypothesis).

In this study, we sorted, purified, coded and entered the data editor of the SPSS software using the survey device. In the secondary level of analysis, inferential statistics (Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient) were employed to determine the strength and direction of the relation between variables. The link between two data sets is shown.

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6\sum d^2}{n^3 - n}$$

The statistical tool is so stated mathematically:

Where d^2 = the difference between the two ranking

n = the number of observations

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4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 4.1 Distribution for indicators of social media adoption for customer relations

	VLE	LE	UD	HE	VHE	N	Min	Max	Mean	S/D	
To what extent does the company systematically collected customer feedback on social media sites?	5	4	1	62	38	110	1.00	5.00	4.1273	.94925	
To what extent does the company develops its relationship with customers through constant communication with them through the means of social media?	6	-	5	60	39	110	1.00	5.00	4.1455	.93687	
To what extent does the company operates through the means of social media in doing customer service activities?	5	2	8	53	42	110	1.00	5.00	4.1364	.96239	
To what extent does the company improved the quality of their products through the study of customer feedback through social media?	5	5	2	57	41	110	1.00	5.00	4.1273	.98716	
To what extent is the company seeking to reach out to new customers through social media?		4	4	8	57	37	110	1.00	5.00	4.0818	.93976

Source: Research Survey, (2021) and SPSS Output.

The table above reveals that the respondents consider social media adoption for customer relations to be a significant feature and attribute of their banks. The results shows a high mean scores of 4.0 and above based on the 5-point likert scale adopted. Which indicated that majority of the respondents affirms to their feelings and experiences that social media for customer relations is an active tool used within their various banks. The result from the analysis indicates that social media for customer relations is considered prevalent and is well acknowledged as a significant instrument used by the deposit money banks. This is as all 5 indicators of the variable assessed are observed to have significant mean distributions (where $x > 2.0$) which reflect the presence of social media for customer relations effective within the examined banks.

4.1 Goal Attainment as a Measure of Organizational Effectiveness

The information on the table 4.2 below reveals the mean distributions of respondents' views on the questionnaire items relating to goal attainment which is the first measure of organizational effectiveness in this study. The measure is assessed based on 5 indicators all stated in positive form.

Table 4.2: Distribution for indicators of goal attainment

	VLE	LE	UD	HE	VHE	N	Mini	Max	Mean	SD
To what extent does this organization constantly monitor established targets to ensure standards are not compromised?	5	4	6	59	36	110	1.00	5.00	4.0636	.96998
To what extent is this organization consistent in the pursuit of resource minimization and process proficiency?	4	4	3	64	35	110	1.00	5.00	4.1091	.90204
To what extent is this organization strong in the assessment of its priorities and key objectives?	4	2	8	56	40	110	1.00	5.00	4.1455	.90702
To what extent does this organization invest substantially in the actualization of service quality?	2	6	6	59	37	110	1.00	5.00	4.1182	.87506
To what extent is this organization strong in sustaining the cohesiveness of its employees and workforce?	2	6	4	64	34	110	1.00	5.00	4.1091	.84967

Source: Field Survey, (2021) and SPSS Output

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The table 4.2 illustrates the mean distributions for the indicators of goal attainment. The results identify goal attainment as having a high evidence (where $x > 2.0$) within the deposit money banks examined in the study. The results show that all 5 indicators project high mean distributions which reflect significant manifestations of goal attainment. This therefore describes the deposit money banks as poised at attaining the numerous goals set by the organization especially with regards to the effectiveness of the deposit money banks.

4.2 Competitiveness as a Measure of Organizational Effectiveness

The information contained in the table 4.10 reveals the various respondents' responses on the test item instruments which measure competitiveness, the second measure of organizational effectiveness. All 5 indicators for the variable are all stated in the positive.

Table 4.3: Distribution for indicators of competitiveness

	VLE	LE	UD	HE	VHE	N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	SD
To what extent is this organization highly innovative?	3	5	5	62	35	110	1.00	5.00	4.1000	.88773
To what extent is this organization driven to standout through creativity?	2	4	4	66	34	110	1.00	5.00	4.1455	.79950
To what extent does this organization follow unique standards that distinguish the organization?	4	4	6	53	43	110	1.00	5.00	4.1545	.95000
To what extent does this organization support change initiatives and ideas?	6	3	5	54	42	110	1.00	5.00	4.1182	1.01124
To what extent does this organization consider quality as an edge and positioning factor?	6	1	7	53	43	110	1.00	5.00	4.1455	.98462

Source: Field Survey, (2021) and SPSS Output

The table 4.3 describes the mean distributions for the indicators of competitiveness. The evidence reveals that a majority of the respondents consider competitiveness as a significant feature and characteristic of organizational effectiveness in the deposit money banks. The results reveal that all indicators of competitiveness as having a high evidence (where $x > 2.0$) within the deposit money banks examined in the study. The results show that all 5 indicators reflect high mean distributions which describe and present the examined banks as being significantly competitive in their desired effectiveness.

4.3 Hypotheses on Social Media Adoption for Customer Relations (SMC) and Organizational Effectiveness Measures

The formulated and tested hypotheses on social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness measures are;

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and goal attainment.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and competitiveness.

Table 4.4: Results of hypothesis test on social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness

			SMC	Goal	Comp
SMC		Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.782**	.631**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000
		N	110	110	110
Spearman's rho	Goal	Correlation Coefficient	.782**	1.000	.639**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
		N	110	110	110
Comp	Comp	Correlation Coefficient	.631**	.639**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.
		N	110	110	110

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2021

Key:

** = Correlation, at 0.01 significant level (2-tailed) i.e. $p < 0.01$

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Rho = Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient

SMC = Social media adoption for customer relations

Goal= Goal attainment

Comp = Competitiveness

- i. Based on the outcome of the analysis above with a correlation (r) value of 0.782 and $P < 0.05$, the null hypothesis one is therefore rejected based on the significance of the relationship between the variables. Thus, there is a significant relationship between social media for customer relations and goal attainment.
- ii. Based on the outcome of the analysis above with a correlation (r) value of 0.631 and $P < 0.05$, the null hypothesis two is therefore rejected based on the significance of the relationship between the variables. Thus, there is a significant relationship between social media for customer relations and competitiveness.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The essence of discussing the finding of a study is to guide the researcher(s) in drawing worthwhile conclusions. Therefore, the discussion of finding in this study was done to establish the outcome of our empirical analysis on the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness as used in this study.

4.4.1 Positive and Significant Relationship between Social Media Adoption for Customer Relations and Organizational Effectiveness

The findings relating to the relationship between social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness showed a positive and significant relationship. It is evident in literature (Schulz and Peltier, 2013; Caruso, 2016), that social media adoption for customer relations is an instrumental subset of social media adoption framework for business organizations including banks which is seen as a vital instrument in the positive development of good social media communication relations between the business and her host of dispersed customers such business organizations.

Previous studies have demonstrated that banks that take full advantage of the opportunities provided by the social media to effectively communicate with customers are likely to be more successful in the highly competitive banking industry (Hoyer and MacInnis, 2010). According to Bughin(2015), the social media provides a lot of communication opportunities for businesses such that if effectively explored organizations can adopt such medium to establish a positive relationship with their customers, identifying their numerous needs through positive communication and reaching out to solve the numerous challenges of customers.

Social media for customer relations also affords the deposit money banks the opportunities to query the stands of their customers concerning the nature and quality of services rendered, through effective relations with customers through the social media; the deposit money banks can assess their performance through the responses of customers. Mangold and Foulds, (2009) concurs to the above when they emphasizes that through the social media, the business organizations can create a direct feedback mechanism allowing customers to express their satisfaction and dissatisfaction concerning the nature of goods and services delivered to the customers by the business enterprise.

Schulz and Peltier(2013), thus posited that social mediafor customer relations provides positive channels for the business to obtain firsthand information directly from source concerning the areas of business transactions where the customers are well satisfied, and those areas where the business enterprise may need to improve on. Therefore social media for customer relations will afford the deposit money banks in Bayelsa State, the opportunities to effectively communicate with their customers, identify their areas of service dissatisfaction and put in place modalities to solve the identified challenges of the customers.

The findings of our investigation in this area thus relates to the position of Kucukemiroglu and Kara(2015), who argued that there is a positive relationship between social media for customer relations and organizational effectiveness. Therefore, our general resolve in this study based on our findings is that social media for customer relation influences organizational effectiveness in deposit money banks in Bayelsa State.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The results and findings of this study reveal that there is a positive and significant relationship between social media adoption for customer relationsand organizational effectiveness (goal attainment and competitiveness). It is therefore concluded that

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deposit money banks that seriously adapted to the social media would positively employ the social media to maintain a positive social relations with customers, which will be instrumental in the success of the deposit money banks in Bayelsa State.

It was also affirmed that the deposit money banks in Bayelsa State take advantage of the opportunities created by the social media to establish a positive and interactive relations with their customers which can make them relatively competitive in the ever dynamic banking industry particularly in Bayelsa State.

5.2 Recommendations

In view of our finding in this study as it relates to social media adoption for customer relations and organizational effectiveness of deposit money banks in Bayelsa States, the following recommendations are thus provided by the researcher; Management of the deposit money banks in Bayelsa State and indeed other States should build a strong media space that will create an opportunity for the banks to reach out to their various customers in effective interrelations that will allow the banks identify and define the challenges of customers and work fast to resolve such challenges; deposit money banks should create an active social media platform that will allow a two way flow of information between the banks and their customer to enable entertain customers complains and make quick and swift response to attend to the general needs of their customers.

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